

The Implication of Macroeconomic Variables on PAKISTAN STOCK EXCHANGE (PSE) Payback and unpredictability before and after Global Economic disaster.

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Abstract-

The reason of this thesis is to examine the implication of macroeconomic issue on the Pakistan Stock exchange instability in pre and post the 2011's worldwide economic disaster (2004-05-2007-08). Worldwide macroeconomic variables utilized in this work are Pakistan stock exchange (PSE) industrial index and gold price, whilst the local macroeconomic variables utilized were the swap rate, mark up rate and inflation factors. This work utilized the different methods to bring the knowledge of the impact of macroeconomic variables on Pakistan stock exchange return instability. Based on the outcome of this work, it was known so as to two variables, specifically PSE and the swap rate had important constructive result on PSE's payback volatility, as three variables those are gold cost, mark up rate and inflation had no important result lying on PSE's payback volatility.

Keywords: Disaster, PSE, Swap rate, Payback, volatility.

Introduction:

Here were two variable evaluate by investors earlier than making investment; payback and its risks. Payback have the shareholder income on investment, white the risk was the differentiation in budgeted payback from the actual payback and threats of securities supposedly include optimistic association, the better the budgeted payback was got, the more the threat have to get, or vice versa. Payback and threat were major's factors to investments of any company, business and macroeconomic circumstances. By globalization plus economic mixing, macroeconomic elements that impact on investment payback and threats were not only local macroeconomic elements but also international elements.

In 2008-09, the United States of America had low rate mark up mortgage problems at the top August 2008-09, when many big financial institutions like American Home Mortgage, New York City, Alliance & Leicester, Ambac and other financial institutions declared bankruptcy. The impact of low rate mortgage in USA, create impact on worldwide economic disaster including Pakistan. Because of this the whole world stock exchange going through a repaid rectification. The economic disaster was not only happened in the USA, it also moved towards the Asia and Europe, including Pakistan. Other stock exchange price index within the worldwide stock exchange experienced through a quick correction. The experimental outcome of research mention that instability in the developed countries stock exchange influenced to others stock exchange, as instability in the growing countries stock exchange were transfer to other stock exchange but not have a such a big effect as compared to developed stock exchange. Instability in the USA had huge influence on the European stock exchange in addition to Asian Stock exchange, but impact of the USA stock exchange to Europe is bigger than Asia.

Because growing capital market, Pakistan Stock Exchange was supposedly impacted with world stock exchange indexes, as compare Indian stock exchange with the USA stock exchange. PSE is the direct correlate price index with the New York Stock Exchange.

Instability is one of major logic in the area of finance. Instability is calculated with the standard deviation or variance of return and is utilized to calculate the threats on economic asset. Major instability describes phases in which comparatively tall variation followed through low instability plus high come back.

Macroeconomic circumstances influence the instability of the stock exchange in a countryside, this was due to macroeconomic factors were the influenced on the company's everyday running operations. The creditability of investors to know and predict macroeconomic situation might be very helpful in manufacture gainful investment decisions making. As a result, an investor would believe a number of macroeconomic indicators might be helpful in deciding investment. Macroeconomic indicators frequently linked to capital markets, variation in mark up rates, the swap rate, inflation, oil rates and

Increase in prices has forever be one of the major macroeconomic problems. At the 2008-09's world financial crisis, stock exchange payback drops rapidly, whilst fluctuations in the inflation rate has increased. However, fluctuations in markup rate and inflation factor have not major impact on stock exchange payback instability.

The variation in markup rates and inflation had a optimistic impact on payback instability but not so important. The mark up rate remains major attractions for every stakeholder to put their investment in shares in order to investment in shares. Here were two justifications how the mark up rate increase can move forward shares prices downward. Firstly, a raise in markup rates changes the scenario

of return on investment. Secondly, rise in mark up rates will short down company earnings. The rise in mark up rates will increase mark up expense issuers, so profit would be down. In addition, whilst mark up rates increase, the cost of manufacturing would be also increase and rates would be increase for the end customers, they might be get expenses of their purchases and reluctant to spending their money .In the end, the manufacturing company's revenues would be fallen down and this will result a decrease in profits that will decrease share prices.

In 2008's global economic crisis, stock exchange returns down rapidly, while mark up rate rise. Constancy, of the swap rate was important due to its impact on the high rank of the country's market. Fluctuation in swap rates could influence on the Stock Exchange indexes in a different way due to vary of mark up rate impact on the outcome of the industries. Impairment of the rupiah can raise the company's profits for export industry, so the worth of the index on the Pakistan Stock Exchange was rising. But the impairment of the rupiah could also drive toward fall in value of index of the Pakistan Stock Exchange for the money market can create more return, so investors were more interested to invest in money market.

Swap rate had negative influence on the Pakistan stock exchange price index. In opposite, of this opinion of authors mentioned that the swap rate had big influence and positive impact on the stock exchange price instability. The similar things were obviously clear where in the 2008's global economic problems the PSE price index was linked rapidly come after by the impairment of the swap rate alongside with the dollar.

Savings in gold was supposed to be more gainful assets due to price drive to boost; gold would also a shape of asset that is more liquid form, because it is acceptable on every country. while the possible payback invest in share or financial instruments would not attractive anymore and not considering to pay compensation involvement of risks, investors would transfer their investment in chattels as such valuable metals(i.e. diamond, gold or stones) or real estate property which would be considered more realistic and secure. It was discovering that gold price had big influence and constructive impact on stock exchange payback. It was described that the change of PSE price index and gold rates since last 11 years generate a higher return, so investors might be more interested in putting their money in the money market.

Research purposes

Base on the study as mentioned above, find out some issues that could be describes as follow :

1. How can the USA stock exchange index impacted on the instability payback of the PSE index before and after the world financial crisis?
2. How can the impact of macroeconomic variables (inflation, swap rate, and interest rate) and the value of gold impact the instability payback of PSE before and after worldwide financial crisis?

Outcomes of study described that the United States stock exchange market situations impact on the local (Pakistan stock exchange) market and the answer specified to the upset of the United States was bigger for the stock exchange of Pakistan market in the state within addition exterior reasons, the circumstance of the local stock exchange market was also impacted by inner issues (local macroeconomic circumstances) .

Objective to evaluate the character of stock exchange payback, and investigate the effect of the diminishing in rupiah alongside with the USA \$ and the impact of oil rates to payback and instability of the shares prices, and to study the threats to equity of the investment organist ion(Financial instruments dealer i.e. stock, securities, bounds) in the mining industries. On the base of study of the impact of macroeconomic variables, it was originated that the swap rate had major influence and adverse relationship with stock exchange payback as the international oil rates had positive and significant effect on stock exchange payback in the mining business. Macroeconomic variables impact on the swap rate and international oil rates beside to instability of the stock exchange described that the swap rate has no major impact on the instability of stock exchange, even as international oil rates had important and adverse impact on the volatility of the mining business.

Objective of analysis that subsistence of pay back instability in few area of worldwide stock exchanges indexes with Pakistan stock exchange, to evaluate the speed reply of payback instability of PSE and to transformation of the instability to other indexes as well as analyze.

Literature review:

According to Aamir M, Rasool N, Fayyaz M, Mumtaz M. (1976), the Arbitrage Pricing Theory (ATP) is another way of linking macroeconomic variables to stock market return. It is an extension of the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) which is based on the mean variance framework by the assumption of the process generating security. In other words, CAPM is based on one factor meaning that there is only one independent variable which is the risk premium of the market. There are similar assumptions between CAPM and APT namely: the assumption of homogenous expectations, perfectly competitive markets and frictionless capital markets [1].

According to Achsani NA. (1976) proposes a multifactor approach to explaining asset pricing through the arbitrage pricing theory (APT). According to him, the primary influences on stock returns are some economic forces such as (1) unanticipated shifts in risk premiums; (2) changes in the expected level of industrial production; (3) unanticipated inflation and (4) unanticipated movements in the shape of the term structure of interest rate. These factors are

denoted with factor specific coefficients that measure the sensitivity of the assets to each factor. APT is a different approach to determining asset prices and it derives its basis from the law of one price [2].

As a matter of fact, in an efficient market, two items that are the same cannot sell at different prices; otherwise an arbitrage opportunity would exist. APT requires that the returns on any stock should be linearly related to a set of indexes as shown in the following equation:

According to Achsani NA, Fauji AJFA, Abdullah P. (1986), individual stock depends on anticipated and unanticipated factors. They believe that most of the return realized by investors is the result of unanticipated events and these factors are related to the overall economic conditions. In fact, although asset returns can also be affected by influences that are not systematic to the economy, returns on large 11 portfolios are mainly influenced by systematic risk because idiosyncratic returns on individual assets are cancelled out through the process of diversification[3].

Achsani NA and Strohe HG. (1999) study the relation between stock returns and macroeconomic variables in Norway. Their results show a positive relationship between oil price and stock returns as well as real economic activity and stock returns. However, their study fails to show a significant relation between stock returns and inflation[4].

Ajireswara A. (2001) analyze the causal relationship between the stock Market and three macroeconomic variables in India's case using the Granger non-causality. These macroeconomic variables are: exchange rate, foreign exchange reserves and trade balance. The results suggest that there is no causal linkage between stock prices and the three variables under consideration.

In their study based on six Asian countries, Doong et al (2005) investigate the relationship between stocks and exchange rates using the Granger causality test. According to their results, there is a significantly negative relation between the stock returns and change in the exchange rates for all the included countries except one[5].

Amaefula CG, Asare BK. Examined the linear relationship between share price and interest rate as well as share price and changes of interest rate. In addition, they also explore the association between changes of share price and interest rate and lastly changes of share price and changes of interest rate in Bangladesh. They find for all of the cases that Interest Rate has significant negative relationship with Share Price and Changes of Interest Rate has significant negative relationship with Changes of Share Price[6].

Methodology:

ARCH-GARCH Data Analysis Methods Models

To help this study, ARCH-GARCH data analysis methods models utilized with the supports of different Eviews 6 software's and Microsoft Excel 2007. ARCH (Auto Regressive Conditional. Heteroscedasticity) was discovered by Engle 1982 to representation the lingering instability that mostly happened to finance statistics.

Fluctuation in payback of Pakistan Stock exchange Price Index could be described in different models that included different variables such as: PSE, Bank rates. Inflation, exchange rate, and the value of chattel (gold) and the restrictive denote models such as heteroskedastic.

Table no 1:

Karachi	Karachi index	j 55,28
Hongkong	Hang Seng Index (HSI)	j 52,45
Singapore	Straits Time Index (STI)	j 50,35
Japan	Nikkei 225 Index (N225)	j 46,69
France	Cotation Assistee en Continu (CAC 40)	j 46,97
Germany	Financial Times Stock Exchange Index (FTSE)	j 37,73
USA	Standard and Poor's 500 (S&P500)	j 43,54
	Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJI)	j 37,15

Table 2 Result of the stationary test

	ARCH (1)	ARCH (2)	GARCH (1,1)	GARCH (2,1)	GARCH (1,2)	GARCH (2,2)
Cor Squared	No	No	No	No	No	No
Residual	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
ARCH LM	No	No	No	No	No	No
test	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Normality	Not Normal	Not Normal	Not Normal	Not Normal	Not Normal	Not Normal

Table no3:

Variable	Koefisien	t-Statistic	Probability
C	0.006548	0.000866	0.0000
DJI	0.637168	0.050551	0.0000
Exchange Rate	0.028933	0.013013	0.0263
Gold	0.014786	0.008039	0.0658
BI rate	-0.007278	0.010926	0.5054
Inflation	-0.000327	0.034571	0.9926
R ²			0.45555814.
F-statistic			48084
Prob (F-statistic)			0.000000

Regression	R ² R ² *
DJI	0,152379 0,463256
Exchange Rate	0,221566
Gold	0,104705
Inflation	0,005965
BI Rate	0,102052

Table no4:

Variable	ADF Value	Critical Value (alpha =%)	Probability	Description
JCI	-1,218714	-2,880212	0,9738	Not stationary
First Difference JCI	-9,702088	-2,880212	0,0000	Stationary at level 1
DJI	-0,383218	-2,880212	0,9078	Not stationary
First Difference DJI	-11,13807	-2,880212	0,0003	Stationary at level 1
LNExchange Rate	-1,322574	-2,880212	0,6184	Not stationary
First Difference LNKurs	-9,093814	-2,880212	0,0000	Stationary at level 1
LNGold	-1,960514	-2,880212	0,3042	Not stationary
First Difference LNGold	-11,12304	-2,880212	0,0000	Stationary at level 1
Inflation	-2,798475	-2,880212	0,0609	Not stationary
First Difference Inflation	-11,07906	-2,880212	0,0000	Stationary at level 1

Statistical Test

Statistical test is to evaluate the figures to be in stationary form or not, could be verified by the Unit Root Test. Dickey-Fuller test is utilized to do this test technique or Augmen Dickey-Fuller test (ADF). Hypothesis utilized for evaluating Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) are as below:

H_0 : There is a unit root/data is not stationary

H_1 : No unit root/data is already stationary

If the probability value $> \alpha = 5\%$ then reject H_0 or mean data is stationary. Conversely, if the probability value $< \alpha = 5\%$ then accept H_0 or meaningful data is not stationary.

Multicollinearity Test:

Multicollinearity test is utilized to evaluate either independent variable X is linked with the other independent variable X or not. to regression each other with Multicollinearity Test utilized was the supported regression method was to execute a regression of each independent variable X with the rest of the independent variables X . After performing auxiliary regression, the regression of coefficient of determination $R^2_{X1X2X3..Xk}$ auxiliary compared to the coefficient of determination R^2 of the original model (Y) with independent variable X . If the coefficient of determination $R^2_{X1X2X2..Xk}$ auxiliary regression is greater than R^2 , the model contains elements of multicollinearity between variables independent and otherwise there is no correlation between the independent variables (Widarjono, 2005).

Autocorrelation Test:

This test has done by using Breusch-Godfrey test. It is also familiar as Lagrange Multiplier test (multiplier lagrange). Breusch-Godfrey test are utilized Hypothesis as:

H_1 : There is currently no autocorrelation in residuals.

If the probability value greater than $> \alpha = 5\%$, then it is not acceptable and H_0 would be refused in other words its mean figures have not having the trouble of autocorrelation.

Heteroscedasticity Test:

Heteroscedasticity test procedure has been done by using White Test. To evaluate either a residual was heteroscedastic or not homoscedastic, a arithmetical test was done by utilizing the hypotheses as below:

H_0 : residuals are homoscedastic

H_1 : residuals are heteroscedastic

If the probability value will be $\text{Obs} \cdot R\text{-square}$ less than $< \alpha = 5\%$ then it will not be acceptable and it will be turned down H_0 or in simple words residuals were heteroscedastic.

Model Selection Criteria:

Test was to evaluate the better option in models. We go through different stages of testing as such: validity/ probability of different model, tests of significance, the coefficient sign test, ARCH effect test and AIC values and SC test.

ARCH Effects Test:

Choosing of a model of ARCH-GARCH on the base of validity decided by residual correlogram test, it contains squared residuals testing and ARCH LM test. It was performed to evaluate either model still having effect of ARCH or not. The persistent of ARCH impact could be found out from the AC and PAC that should not be major one (greater than 0.05) and also the major level that is not less than the level of confidence ($\alpha = 5\%$) (AgusWidarjono 2005). This model is a perfect model if it could not have ARCH impact with major value of AC and PAC (less than 0.05).

Value of SC and AIC Test:

The study of the statistics, we could reach a conclusion of have few best models. If more than other alternatives models that is also good for us, there could be relative numerical information. That numerical information must be comparable with AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) and SC (Scharz Criterion). The following shape of the equation of those parameters is:

Autocorrelation Test:

It could be performed by Breusch-Godfrey test. It is also familiar as Lagrange Multiplier test (multiplier lagrange). Hypothesis Utilized in Breusch-Godfrey test were:

Table 2 mentioned, facts for the independent variable markup rate (BP interest rate) was remain immovable at point whilst the dependent variable and the others independent variables PSE index, exchange rate, gold rate and inflation factors were not stationary so we have to differential the statistics which are in rank of stationary. We came to conclusion after the first differencing, that statistics were remaining stationary at the 5% level.

The outcome of the auxiliary regression establish that on the basis of the value of R^2 is lesser than the main model regression R^{*2} so we came to conclusion that it still existence of multicollinearity issue among independent variables.

Model For Measuring PSE's instability payback:

To create a model for evaluating the PSE index payback instability it was needed that figures as such PSE stock index, swap rate, gold rate, mark up rate (BP interest) and inflation factors. In this research, figures were used starting from the period January 2002 to December 2014.

Autocorrelation Test:

Breusch-Godfrey test reproduced *Obs*R-squared* probability value of 0.1366, this value is more than 5% a significances level so it will result in rejection of H_0 .

Heteroscedasticity Test:

Tests on the conditional mean squared residual equation with *White test* probability values showed that *Obs * R-square* of 0.0012 is lesser than $\alpha = 5\%$, so we came to results that of the rejection of H_0 or its other means that the statistics was heteroscedastic to use ARCH-GARCH is good choice for us to estimate the volatility.

Model:

Parameter estimation of ARCH-GARCH (p, q) model used *maximum likelihood* methods or *Quasi Maximum Likelihood* (QML). This model combines simulation $p = 0, 1$ and 2 with a value of $q = 0, 1$ and 2 . The results of the estimation of all alternative models of ARCH-GARCH then compared to one another, the first thing noticed is the feasibility/validity of the model, then in terms of significance, the sign of coefficients, AIC and SC with the smallest value are selected as the best model.

Appraisal/authenticity of ARCH-GARCH models is done with residual test including squared residual correlogram test, histogram-normality test and ARCH-LM test. Based on the *Correlogram squared residuals test* and *ARCH-LM test* as shown in Table 4, six models are free of ARCH effect and the data is not distributed normally. Then the next phase is comparing the significance, sign of coefficients, and the value of AIC and SC. From The result of estimation appeared that the model ARCH (1), ARCH (2), GARCH (1,1) and GARCH (1,2) and GARCH (2,2) have two significant variables while GARCH (2,1) has three significant variables.

The coefficient sign test results showed that the coefficients sign of model ARCH (1) and ARCH (2) have two variables that have the same coefficient sign as the sign of hypothesis variable coefficients, which are variable DJI and Gold. GARCH (1,1) and GARCH (1,2) have three variables that have the same coefficient signs as hypothesis variable coefficients signs, which are variables DJI, Gold and BI rate. While GARCH (2,1) and GARCH (2,2) have four variables that have the same coefficient signs as hypothesis variable coefficients sign, which are variable DJI, Gold, BI rate and inflation.

The best model is the model that has the smallest value of AIC and SC. Based on the AIC and SC test, GARCH (2,1) is the model that has the smallest AIC and SIC compared to five other models. So, GARCH (2,1) was chosen as the best model for analysis.

Interpretation Results:

On the basis of the feasibility test, GARCH (2,1) was the good model that would be utilized for this research. The following Table 5 presented a statistical test/test of significance of the regression results GARCH (2,1).

Pakistan Stock Exchange Index:

PSE variable had lesser value than the probability of the level of 0.05 which is 0.00. It came to result that variable PSE have a huge impact on PSE payback instability. Coefficient value of PSE is 0.637169, which results that if risk rate of PSE return stock index increase to 1%, the risk level of the PSE stock index payback will also arise by 0.637169%, *ceteris paribus*. The consequences gained by research are dependable with the hypothesis that has been created at the start, that the payback instability has significant constructive impact on PSE payback instability.

Globalization and economic integration cause the economy of a country are related so that enables volatility's transmission from one country to another. Therefore, changes in the stock exchanges will also be transmitted to other countries, where the larger exchanges (NYSE) will affect the smaller exchanges (IDX). The results in this study obtained that the DJI index return volatility significantly affect JCI, this proves that there is an integration between the stock market in the US with stock market in Indonesia in the period of the study.

Exchange Rate:

Exchange rate variable was the lesser than the probability of 0.05 level which is 0.0263. On the basis of the value of exchange rate variable, It have a great impact on the PSE. The coefficient value of the exchange rate is 0.028932, as a result exchange rate increases (impaired) by 1% , so risk level of the PSE stock index will increase by 0.028932% *ceteris paribus*. The outcome gain from the research disagree with the hypothesis that would have been created at the start that exchange rate have positive or adverse impact on PSEs payback volatility.

The outcome were dependable with the outcome gained by Jayadin (2012) which results as such that the exchange rate optimistically impact on the instability of stock payback of the energy and mining sectors in Pakistan Stock Exchange and the research outcome by Prio (2010) which mentioned that the exchange rate has a positive impacted on the PSE's payback instability.

As opposite to these results, the outcome of this study performed by Erdogan&Ozale (2005) which mentioned that the deteriorating in currency value in the country (USA) it would result in a decrease in the unpredictability of stock payback pre and post the crisis tenures of 1994-95

The F-statistic

As mentioned in Table 5, the value of F-statistic obtained at 13.48083 and the value of the probability of F is 0.0000 which was lesser than the value of $\alpha = 5\%$ (0.05). It means, the independent variable is PSE, exchange rate, the rate of gold

Gold Price

Gold variable had larger value than the probability of 0.05 levels which is 0.0656. On the basis of the variable gold have no major impact on PSE with coefficient value of gold is 0.014785.

We came to conclusion after this research that is constant with the results of research performed by (Lawrence 2013) which described that the values of gold have no major impact Pakistan Stock Exchange price index. It was also described by Rusbariand (2012), in his study he concluded that the value of gold had no major impact on Pakistan stock exchange price index. Again the repeated nature of study also did by Naziret *al* (2010), he also mentioned the same things.

Test Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The outcome from regression gained that R^2 value is 0.455557; it showed that for 45.56% of the variation of PSE payback instability fluctuation around the study phase could be described by variations in the five different independent variables utilized in this study. Whilst the rest of 54.44% was described by other means of external variables to the model. Other elements that may impacted on the PSE were other local macroeconomic elements beyond the utilized of variables, for say redundancy, economic and political conditions of Pakistan, oil rates and other worldwide macroeconomic elements (Wijaya 2010)

Interest Rate of Bank of Pakistan (BP Rate)

Interest rate has more value than the of 0.05 level which is 0.5053. On the basis of the values, Interest rate have not big influence on the PSE with coefficient value of -0.007279. These outcomes are the same as with research performed by Abd, Kadir, Selamat, Masuga and Taudi (2011). While their study Abd, Kadir, Selamat, Masuga and Taudi (2011) create that the impact of the interest rate on the payback instability of Kuala Lumpur Composite Index (KLIC) was not as influential as it should be, so that interest rate variable in forecasting of the instability of stock payback was consider weak.

After the research (Wijaya 2008) concluded that the interest rate (BP rate) had significant and adverse impact on mining industrial area stock returns in the Pakistan Stock Exchange. The same theory also discover by Naziret *al* (2010), Eryigit (2012), Javed&Akhtar S (2012), they came to conclusion that the interest rate had significant and adverse impact on stock payback.

Inflation:

Variable of Inflation had larger value than the probability of 0.05 level which is 0.9925. On the basis of value, the inflation variable have no major impact on PSE with coefficient of inflation is -0.000326.

Amaefula and Asare (2014) described that different previous research stated about inflation correlation with stock payback. Few researches were in theory agreed with the hypothesis of classical economics whilst the others had different opinion on the basis of experimental conclusion of Engle (2004), Engle and Rangel 2005) and Rizwan (2007) discover that inflation had strong projecting tool for stock exchange market volatility and stock market payback. Whilst the study of Habibullah et al. (2009) evaluates the impact of inflation on payback instability and on the Asian countries stock markets, such as Pakistan, Japan, India, and the Malaysia. Their research discovers that movement in macroeconomic elements which determined inflation had no such significant influence on the stock return and instability. It is not as stronger as it should be.

As opposing to above, a study performed by Skendra (2005) discover that inflation would impact on the blue chip shares.

CONCLUSION

The variables utilized in this research had high instability and were heteroscedastic so OLS regression models unadjusted to utilize in this study. For the figures was volatile and heteroscedastic, ARCH-GARCH model is a good options to evaluate the statistics. The right choice of ARCH-GARCH model was selected in this research is GARCH (2,1). If we correlate the worldwide economic correlation of the instability of PSE there is not only the international factors but a lot of domestic macrocosmic variable too. Only the one factor which impact on the PSE return is the international stock index (Dow Jones Industrial Average). DJI had more influential impact on the PSE return and instability. In other if there is movement in Dow Jones Industrial Average stock index would also Impacted on the PSE stock exchange index in Pakistan.

Local macroeconomic variable that impacted on the PSE's volatility return was the exchange rate. This variable also had significant and positive impact on PSE's volatility return, it conclude that the boost in exchange rate (impairment of rupiah against the USA \$) might raise the level of threat in stocks, and vice versa. Whilst BP rate, inflation, and gold rate may not have major impact on the PSE's return volatility.

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